

SCENARIOS FOR SOUTH-WEST MESSINIA

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CONTEXTUAL ELEMENTS INFLUENCING SCENARIO BUILDING

The vision developed by the stakeholders of South-west Messinia is based on the ideal of achieving a sustainable and balanced interaction with the environment through processes that are dynamic and allow the system to be resilient to external and internal pressures and shocks. In order to develop strategic policy guidelines and business solutions supporting the pathways towards this resilient future, it is important to be able to measure the system's vulnerability to shocks, to identify possible tipping points and to explore barriers and drivers for transformation. Scenarios are useful tools to explore possible futures and to identify opportunities and threats in order to achieve this desired goal.

The coastal part of the South-west Messinia case study is designated as a NATURA 2000 area. However, due to a lack of environmental management several habitats of the site are under pressure (Maneas et al., 2019). When the COASTAL project began, in 2018, there was no acting environmental Management Body in the area. In 2019, a Management Body was established, though along the way the status of this body changed again due to shifts in national policy. At present, the state is about to finalize the consultation process of the updated Special Environmental Study (SES) for the area and to assign the management of the site to a public Management Body.

Thus, to support the environmental management of the area, the scenario building process aimed to also provide suggestions for the management of the Gialova Lagoon, which is the coastal wetland which has been degraded by past anthropogenic activities and is in urgent need of measures for its restoration (Maneas et al., 2019; Maneas et al., 2020, Bray et al 2022). Moreover, the restoration of the wetland is central to the vision developed by the stakeholders, as it was identified as essential to fishing and tourism activities and is linked to agricultural practices at a catchment scale.

The COASTAL outcomes are expected to support the overall management of the area. The local COASTAL partners, and in particularly NEO, are in close contact with the relevant national authorities (NECCA). Suggestions for enhanced monitoring and actions that will improve the water management of the wetland (restoration) have already been imported in the updated SES.

STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT DURING THE SCENARIO BUILDING PROCESS

PROJECT PARTNERS

The scope of the modelling work for South-west Messinia was determined based on the outcomes of the first workshop organized in the context of the COASTAL project, as well as our current understanding (Bray et al., 2022; Maneas et al., 2019; Maneas et al., 2020; Manzoni et al., 2020; Berg et al., 2018; COASTALD33). The visionary exercise developed during that workshop also served as a baseline for building up the scenarios that are presented here. These scenarios were then further discussed and developed with local and regional project partners. Preliminary results were shared and discussed with all interested parties in a second workshop. The tables below give a more detailed view of the organizations involved.

Organisation	Type of organisation	Expertise	Number of participants	M	V	X
TEMES SA	Tourism company	Tourism development	3	3		
Captain Vasilis Foundation (CVF)	Foundation	Sustainable agricultural development	3	3		
Development Agency of Messinia (DAM)	Anonymous company administrated by the sub-regional government of Messinia	Regional development	3	1	2	

OTHER STAKEHOLDERS

In order to cover all needed expertise, also other local and regional stakeholders were involved in the workshops. Their details are summarized in the table below.

Organisation	Type of organisation	Expertise	Number of participants	M	V	X
Sub-region of Messinia	Regional government	Agriculture and fishing	3	1	2	
Municipal Water Agency	Municipality	Water management	1	1		
Forestry Agency	Public sector	Forest management	2	2		
Ephorate of Archaeology	Public sector	Antiquities protection and management	1		1	
Management Body	Public sector	Environmental management	1	1		
Nileas	Local farmers' cooperative	Olive oil production	1	1		
Agricultural Cooperative Messinia Union	Farmers' union	Agriculture	1	1		
Ben Olive Mill	Olive mill	Olive oil production and agritourism	1	1		
Gialova Association of Enterprises	Local association	Local economy	2	2		

Organisation	Type of organisation	Expertise	Number of participants	M	V	X
Yialova Lagoon	Fish company	Fishing and sport-fishing	1	1		
Explore Messinia	Tourism company	Ecotourism	1	1		
University of Kalamata	University	Cultural management	1		1	
Hellenic Ornithological Society	NGO	Birds conservation	1	1		
Archelon	NGO	Sea turtle conservation	1	1		

RATIONALE STAKEHOLDER SELECTION

In South-west Messinia, the Greek case study, tourism expansion and associated infrastructure development, such as hotels, roads and airports, provide opportunities for diversified livelihoods, but also increase the pressure on agricultural land, water resources and the natural environment (Tiller et al., 2019; Maneas et al., 2019; Klein et al., 2014). The area produces olive oil of high quality. However, current circumstances, such as small parcels of land, the (un)willingness to cooperate and CAP eligibility criteria for direct support when adopting agri-environmental measures (Damianos and Giannakopoulos, 2002, Lastra-Bravo et al, 2015), have added limitations to the sustainable growth potential of the sector (D1: Tiller et al., 2019). Today, the production of olives is mainly based on conventional farming practices (e.g., tillage, use of pesticides, herbicides and synthetic fertilizers), which results in severe environmental degradation of coastal and marine areas (COASTAL D33; Berg et al., 2018).

The operation of pomace-mills, located in industrial zones outside the catchment area, should ensure that olive-mill’s waste is not disposed in the environment, but are treated as useful by-products that are further processed to produce other types of olive-oil and products (D1: Tiller et al., 2019). Unfortunately, not all olive-mills follow the regulations and their operation impacts the environment. Meanwhile, the wetland is in a bad environmental state (Bray et al, 2022), and unless actions are taken towards the restoration of hydrological conditions and the enhancement of its ecosystem services, it is expected that it may soon collapse.

In summary, this Greek case study is led by the research institutes NEO/SU, and HCMR. Additionally, it includes TEMES SA, CVF and DAM, as well as the stakeholders mentioned above and other parties that may benefit from the project’s outcomes. NEO/SU is located in the case study area and has a wide network of stakeholders with whom they collaborate in research and educational projects. HCMR has a long tradition in marine and wetland research in the area. Furthermore, TEMES owns the biggest touristic development in the area, CVF is a foundation focusing on the sustainable development of agriculture in Messinia and DAM is a company of the sub-region of Messinia which has the responsibility, among others, to administrate LEADER projects in the Messinia region. Thus, the selection of our stakeholders was based on suggestions from each of these partners and was followed then by the snowballing method.

SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT APPROACH

The people who contributed to the scenarios for South-west Messinia were involved from the first COASTAL workshop on, which took place in June 2019. During that workshop, the participants were

Table 1. Overview of the main meetings in the scenario development process.

1	Meeting with	Nileas
	When?	2020
	Main goal	Discussions to improve our understanding about olive-oil production: cultivation practices, irrigation patterns, role of cooperatives, production & sales, farmers' well-being, etc.
2	Meeting with	Municipal Water Agency
	When?	2020
	Main goal	Discussions to improve our understanding about municipal water supply system and waste-water management.
3	Meeting with	University of Ioannina
	When?	2021
	Main goal	Discussions to improve our understanding about fish in lagoon environments and associated ecosystem services.
4	Meeting with	Municipality
	When?	2021
	Main goal	Discussions to improve our understanding about mosquito management and solid waste management.
5	Meeting with	Interviews with project partners
	When?	2021
	Main goal	In-depth semi-structured interviews to improve the narratives and projections of the SSPs at local level.
6	Meeting with	Consultancy assigned to implement the update of the SES (NERCO)
	When?	2021
	Main goal	In-depth discussions for the integration of suggestions for enhanced monitoring and actions that will improve the water management of the wetland (restoration) within the updated SES.

engaged in a visionary exercise, where they were asked to agree on a common goal. Next, they had to identify enablers and barriers to achieve this goal through a back casting exercise. This process formed the baseline of our scenario development approach. The resulting common goal or vision can be summarized as: ***“Join forces in creating the Brand Name of Sustainable Messinia that expands across all sectors, activities and products”*** (D1: Tiller et al., 2019).

In particular, the MAL participants suggested that priority actions should consider the elements below:

- Adoption of an **integrated and eco-friendly model of olive-oil production**.
- Adoption of a **sustainable (resilient) low-impact tourism** model to reduce the impacts of mass 3S (Sea, Sand, Sun) tourism.
- Enhancement of **environmental management in protected and sensitive areas including a better monitoring of natural resources**.
- **Improvement of solid and liquid waste management**.

During a second workshop, which took place in March 2020, the participants were further introduced into the concepts of scenarios and transition pathways. They were asked to prioritize actions that can enable the pursuit of the commonly defined vision, as well as possible adaptation measures to

mitigate climate change. The discussions about actions and adaptation measures were useful to downscale the SSPs to the case area.

The restrictions due to the pandemic limited active interactions with the stakeholders, but the use of online questionnaires provided useful input for the scenario building process. When these restrictions were lifted, the case coordinators decided to have an additional in-person meeting to further validate scenario development, which took place in March 2021. During this additional meeting we were able to use the 3 Horizons framework and identified possible signs that stirr the area either towards a more sustainable pathway or towards the current business as usual model. We used these discussions to validate, revise or further inform the scenario storylines. Complementary to the inputs provided during these three workshops, the scenario building process also received inputs and insights during meetings with our partners and with local and scientific experts.

Figure 1: Overview of the scenario building process.

THE SCENARIOS IN RELATION TO THE SYSTEM DYNAMICS MODEL

As the scenarios for South-west Messinia deal with uncertainties external to the modelled system, they cannot be understood correctly without knowing the exact delineation of this system. What is 'in'? And what is 'out'? What is part of the modelled system? And what is not? This section therefore gives a brief introduction to the system dynamics model developed within COASTAL for this area. Next, an overview is given of the external uncertainties in the system's environment that were taken as a starting point to develop the scenarios.

WHAT DID WE MODEL?

The system dynamics model for South-west Messinia covers an area of approximately 250 km², which is divided into four hydrological catchments. The model consists of several views (sub-models) that are separately developed and quantified, yet well interlinked. The model is designed to holistically address the main elements associated with the pursuit of the common vision for the area (cfr. previous section) under different scenarios and uncertainties (e.g. climate change, tourism development, restoration efforts, etc.). It is well connected to national and European policies. This means that concepts such as "ecosystem services", which is increasingly used within new EU strategies, are also incorporated in the model. (The detailed structure of the model is described in Viaene et al., 2020 and Viaene et al., 2021.)

In relation to the common vision of the area, some key topics and problems (and their interactions) that are addressed in the SW Messinia model are:

- The role of cooperatives in achieving the transition from conventional to integrated and eventually organic farming practices (e.g. branding and marketing, negotiation strength, certified production & agritourism). How is this beneficial for the farmers' well-being? And how can this be enhanced in the coming years (links with future projects and business opportunities)?
- The expected benefits of the transition (conventional to integrated/organic farming) on:
 - the environment (e.g. use of groundwater resources and salinization risk, use of chemical pesticides and fertilizers, water quality);
 - the characteristics of olive orchards (e.g. soil organic content, soil erosion, soil biodiversity, vegetation cover);
 - the well-being of farmers (e.g. costs for fertilizing and pest control, olive-oil price);
 - the branding and marketing of local products;
 - the attractiveness of the landscape and the promotion of agritourism.
- The effect of seasonal (mass) tourism on (and associated feedbacks):
 - the environment (e.g. use of groundwater resources and salinization risk, beach degradation);
 - the land use change trend (olive orchards to built-up land) and associated impacts on the area's character and naturalness.
- The urgency for wetland restoration actions to prevent the collapse of the ecosystem and to secure and enhance the below:
 - biodiversity conservation and development of eco-tourism;
 - fish production and food security;
 - area attractiveness and tourism.

WHAT KIND OF EXTERNAL UNCERTAINTIES WERE TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT?

The SW Messinia SD model describes possible future shifts relative to the pursuit of the common vision for the region. These shifts will be partly determined by system external factors and uncertainties that cannot be controlled by actors active within the system, such as droughts and forest fires due to climate change or fluctuating energy prices. In the SD model these uncertainties are entered via scenarios built up from a combination of Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs), complemented with insights from IPCC reports, and the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs).

The basic RCP used in the Greek model is RCP 2.6, as there were no climatic projections available conform an RCP1.5. Given the latest insights in the evolution of climate change, this was not considered a major problem. Moreover, some researchers (Vautard et al., 2014; Koutroulis et al, 2016) expect that the Mediterranean temperature change will be at least one degree higher than the global average anyway. Additionally, we have also run the model against an RCP 8.5 to test the model's behaviour under extreme conditions.

To downscale the global SSPs to the case study level we made use of the narratives and projections developed by Reimann, Merken and Vafeidis (2017) for the Mediterranean Coastal Zones. These narratives and projections were further specified based on the narratives developed by the case's stakeholders during workshops and other discussion moments. Further input came from the trends published by Mitter et al., 2020 in relation to the future of agricultural activities.

In the table below, an overview is given of the parameters from these scenarios that are expected to affect the future behavior of the modelled system. The second column displays the input variables where the scenarios connect with the modelled system. The third column lists the parameters from the generic scenario framework that were taken into consideration to explain the future evolution of these model-specific input variables.

Table 2. Model input variables in relation to system-external uncertainties.

N°	Model input variable	System-external uncertainties affecting this model input variable
1	Precipitation, Evapotranspiration & Evaporation	Climate change
2	Cooperative Capacity	Agro-food policies, agro-food industry development, consumer choices, social equity and social cohesion
3	Water Demand	Population, technology, climate change, public and private investments and resource availability
4	Sustainable Food Production (Demand)	Population, global economy, energy costs, public and private investments, global social and environmental awareness
5	Coastal Tourism	Global economy, energy costs, technological advancements
6	Secondary Housing	Population, migration
7	Policy Implementation	National policies

DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE SCENARIOS

In total, we developed 4 scenarios for South-west Messinia. Each of them is rooted in the combination of a certain SSP with a climate scenario linked to a certain RCP. The following overview shows the combinations used during the scenario building process:

- Scenario 1 (SSP1 + RCP2.6): Green, integrated road
- Scenario 2 (SSP2 + RCP2.6): Unorganized, middle road
- Scenario 3 (SSP4 + RCP2.6): Divided road
- Scenario 4 (SSP5 + RCP2.6): Rapid development

In the remaining part of this section, future evolutions under each of these four scenarios are described qualitatively making use of each of the variables listed in the second column of Table 2 above. Via the following repository link all quantitative data corresponding with these qualitative descriptions can be accessed easily: <https://zenodo.org/communities/773782-coastal/?page=1&size=20>

1. CLIMATE VARIABLES: PRECIPITATION, EVAPOTRANSPIRATION & EVAPORATION

The climate variables that are used in the SD model for South-west Messinia, cover the precipitation (P), evapotranspiration (PET) and evaporation (E) rates. The variables “P-PET inland”, “P-PET coastal” and “P-E lagoon” (inputs or outputs in m/Year), are used to describe the water exchanges with the atmosphere (see also Figure 2).

The variable “Tourism Climate Index (TCI)” is kept constant as we have assumed that, although there will be a reduction in summer arrivals due to an average temperature increase, there will most probably be an increase in arrivals during the rest of the year. Hence, the overall annual trend will not be affected. This decision is in line with what others have estimated for tourism in Greece, which is expected to be less vulnerable than other destinations (Koutroulis A., et al. 2018).

Figure 2: Annual changes in climatic variables in the Greek case study, under RCP 2.6 (coastal areas as P-PET coastal) projected for different (RCPs) during the years 2010-2100. Long-term annual average precipitation for RCP2.6 is equal to 332 mm/yr, indicating a decrease of about 8,5% compared with the long-term annual average for 1971-2010 (362 mm/yr - Reference condition).

2. VARIABLE: COOPERATIVE CAPACITY

“Cooperative capacity” is defined as the ability of partners in a partnership to collaborate towards the partnership’s goals. It is a dimensionless parameter that affects the flow variable “willingness of farmers” directly, as more cooperation leads to an increase of the cooperative’s membership. Partnership development is one of the main Sustainable Development Goals (SDG17), but its successful implementation is affected by both system internal and external factors, as a result of which it is recognized to be one of the main uncertainties for the system of Messinia. As a value it depends on (Vayaliparampil et al., 2021):

- The development of a common understanding or vision that includes a shared interpretation of the roles and processes in the partnership.
- The level of equity in shared governance roles and decision-making experienced by all partners within the partnership.
- The level of trust between the partners.

In addition, as we are referring to cooperatives based on sustainable agricultural practices, their cooperative capacity will also depend on policy choices in associated domains, such as agriculture, nature and economy, evolutions in the agri-food industry and consumer choices (Grashuis J., 2018).

Figure 3, which can be found on page 16, shows the expected evolution in cooperative capacity under each of the SSPs. The reference value for this variable is set at 0.2 and its maximum is 1.

Green, integrated road

Societies start to collaborate to achieve common goals and to form integrated partnerships (Vayaliparampil, et al., 2021). Global examples from successful collaborations are widely disseminated as pilot models for a sustainable future. Policies are supportive to sustainable and collaborative practices by means of financial support and the promotion of inclusive governance. Consumers select high-quality products and the agro-food industry supports sustainable farming. Equitable practices and autonomy build trust and understanding among farmers. Under this scenario, “cooperative capacity” increases rapidly, showing a mean increase of around 245% (from 0.200 to 0.690).

Unorganized, middle road

In this scenario partners have invested in a vision, though they often follow their own work plans. As a result, they tend to work only haphazardly towards the achievement of the vision (Vayaliparampil, et al., 2021). There is a reduced level of agency and equity under these circumstances, hence success is much more dependent on outside drivers, such as policies and supporting subsidies, making existing partnerships more vulnerable. A small percentage of farmers continues to collaborate. And if successful, these collaborations will attract more partners. Under this scenario, “cooperative capacity” increases slowly, showing a mean increase of around 61% (from 0.200 to 0.261).

Divided road

There is no clear vision. Farmers might work together when it suits their own interests and practices. As poverty is increasing and societies fragment more and more, there is no equity or governance shared among participants. European agricultural policies increasingly support economic growth and technology development, from which the large, industrialized farms benefit the most. The interests of a large proportion of society are mostly ignored (Mitter et al, 2020). Co-operatives and local agro-food initiatives are rare, as global agri-business players dominate the supply chains. Under this scenario, “cooperative capacity” is reduced significantly and shows a mean value of around 61% (from 0.200 to 0.078).

Rapid development

A dominant partner often dominates the vision, mission and strategy of cooperations, as a result of which partnerships are often dependent on the dominant partner's directives (Vayaliparampil, et al., 2021). The relationship between farmers and the rest of society is deteriorating because of a high degree of individualization and egocentrism (Mitter et al, 2020). Public payments to agricultural and food systems are drastically reduced conform the paradigms ruling liberalized and integrated markets. Environmental standards are lowered considerably, which results in an overexploitation of natural resources. Furthermore, people adopt new dietary habits based on technological advancements (Mitter et al, 2020), which causes a decrease in the global demand for olive oil. As a consequence, more and more farmers choose to sell their properties for built-up land. Under this scenario, the overall effect of these evolutions results in a gradual decrease of "cooperative capacity", showing a mean value of around 31% (from 0.200 to 0.139).

3. VARIABLE: WATER DEMAND

The current average annual domestic water consumption was estimated based on the historical average consumption of 288 L/day/capita. Global SSP scenarios do not provide any specific qualitative descriptions of possible future water demand, although it is expected that there will be an increase due to changes in climatic conditions (Koutroulis, et al 2016). The input variable "water demand" is a dimensionless parameter linked to the variables "per capita water demand" and "per tourism water demand". The reference value for this input variable is set at 1. Figure 3 (cfr. page 16) shows the expected evolution in water demand under each of the SSPs.

Green, integrated road

Under this scenario, there is a slight decrease in water demand, which is related to increased awareness and more efficient usage both in agriculture and in tourist facilities (Reimann et al, 2017; Koutroulis et al, 2016). This results in a slight decrease of the water demand, which is given a reference value of 1 to a mean value of 0.91.

Unorganized, middle road

Koutroulis et al., (2016) suggest that realistic future scenarios of irrigation demand are based on local development plans and proposed strategies for an expansion of the irrigation networks. Other information that was taken into account was any relevant information in the SSPs linked to the area of irrigated land and data about crop intensity. The overall conclusion was that water demand in this scenario 2 is affected more by internal system actions than external factors, and hence remains stable with regards to the SSP changes.

Divided road & Rapid development

Under these scenarios the private sector makes efforts to increase productivity and human well-being with new technologies, but focuses less on resource efficiency. As a result, lifestyles are more resource- and energy- intensive and resource demands rise. This results in increasing pressures on land, water, and biodiversity (Mitter, 2020). In both scenarios, the effect of water demand is therefore increased with 9% (from 1 to 1,09).

4. VARIABLE: SUSTAINABLE FOOD PRODUCTION (DEMAND)

The input variable “sustainable food production” is a dimensionless parameter linked to the variables “transition factors” and “local tourism demand for sustainable olive-oil production”, which are both part of the part of the model that describes interactions within the agricultural sector. The reference value for this input variable is set at 0.1. Figure 3 below shows the expected evolution in “sustainable food production” under each of the SSPs.

Green, integrated road

Under this scenario, the impact of sustainable food production is increased by 60% (from 0.1 to 0.16). This is because of consumer demands that favour the supply of multiple ecosystem services (Mitter et al., 2020), which goes along with more farmer engagement in the area. The demand for ecosystem services gives rise to a stable pace of structural changes in agriculture, also favoring producers and producer cooperatives.

Unorganized, middle road

Under this scenario, the degree of sustainable food production remains unchanged and equals 0.1. The demand for locally produced food, as well as for plant-based protein/meat alternatives, increases very slowly. Yet, because there is no organized support in the area, this has little impact. A large share of the population still consumes convenient and highly processed food. Minimum standards are set at the European level, but individual countries can decide on more rigorous standards. Their implementation depends on policy decisions (see also the scenarios covering policy implementation).

Divided road

Inequalities in education and income prevail in the agricultural sector. This results in a very diverse farming population in terms of age, education level, innovative capacity and migration background (Mitter et al 2020). Under this scenario, sustainable food production decreases by 30% (from 0.1 to 0.07).

Rapid development

European decision-makers have a strong interest in trade liberalization. In line with this paradigm they continue to strengthen and invest in multi-lateral trading systems at the global level. This further increases competition in the agricultural sector (Mitter, 2020). This liberalized agricultural model favours high-tech, large farming businesses and the consumption of processed food. It is difficult for small-scale producers to follow the trends of rapid development without financial support. As a result, sustainable food production decreases with 60% (from 0.1 to 0.04).

5. VARIABLE: COASTAL TOURISM

The input variable “coastal tourism” is a dimensionless parameter linked to the flow variable “new beds”, which is used to calculate the variable “tourism growth rate” and the stock “beds availability”. The latter gives the annual number of beds in the area (existing and new). The reference value for this input variable is set at 1, which in the model means that tourism will follow current growth rates (Viaene et al., 2021). Figure 3 (cfr. page 16) shows the expected evolution in coastal tourism under each of the scenarios.

The storylines of these scenarios were based on interviews with the main developer in the area (TEMES) and the study by Reimann et al. from 2016. Similar to the latter, we decided to follow the approach of not only considering the number of tourists arriving, but also the type of tourists visiting the area, and whether they would have an interest to diversify their activities instead of following the traditional 3S-model.

Green, integrated road

Under this scenario there is still an increase in the number of arrivals, though the growth rate is slightly reduced compared with current trends. The reason for this, is that people tend to choose destinations that are closer to their homes or where they can travel to by car. However, as the COVID restrictions have showed, a reduction in the number of flights, or even imposing a ban on flying for a number of months, has little to no impact on the number of people arriving in Messinia. It is not an island and therefore easy to reach by car. As a result, the most important change that can be expected, is a shift in the type of tourists. With the right investments, more and more tourists are expected to select this destination for its natural value and its adjacency to a Natura2000 site. Under this scenario, "coastal tourism" therefore gradually decreases with 12% (from 1 to 0.88).

Unorganized, middle road & Rapid development

Under both these scenarios the tourism sector continues to grow, showing a mean increase of this variable of around 61% (from 1 to 1.61). In the scenario "rapid development" also a significant increase is observed in the visitors opting for the 3S-model, as there is less interest in this scenario for high-quality tourism. In the scenario "unorganized, middle road", on the other hand, there is a continuation of current trends. This means that most tourists will still come to the area for its sandy beaches, yet certain groups will also show interest in the area's natural assets.

Divided road

Under this scenario coastal tourism increases with, on average, 31% (from 1 to 1.31). This implies a slower growth rate than in the former two scenarios. The reason for this is that tourism will continue to grow for the elites only, which means that one can expect a decline in mass tourism. However, as the area caters to the elite tourism growth rates are expected to remain high.

6. VARIABLE: SECONDARY HOUSING

The input variable "secondary housing" is a dimensionless parameter linked to the flow variable "new houses", which is used to calculate the stock "secondary houses". The latter gives the annual number of secondary houses in the area (existing and new). The reference value for this variable is set at 1. Figure 3 below shows the expected evolution in secondary houses under each of the scenarios.

Green, integrated road

Under this scenario agriculture gains more and more support, as a result of which the trend of land use changes towards private properties with secondary homes gradually comes to an end. Restrictive policies (Reimann, et al 2017) further inhibit the urbanisation of rural coastal areas. The value shows a mean decrease of around 61% (from 1 to 0.39).

Unorganized, middle road & Rapid development

Under both scenarios population growth in coastal rural areas of the north Mediterranean is mainly

driven by tourism and second home ownership. The population in coastal areas increases because most economic activities are located, which results in a high urbanisation rate (Reimann, et al, 2017). A lack of spatial planning policies remains a major problem in these scenarios. There are not enough constraints therefore to limit the building of secondary houses. Consequentially, the variable “secondary housing” increases with 61% (from 1 to 1.61).

Divided road

As in this scenario coastal development is driven by the interests of the elite, the coastal population is expected to further grow based on an influx of tourists and the expansion of areas for secondary homes (Reimann, et al, 2017). Under this scenario, the variable “secondary housing” is therefore increased with about 31% (from 1 to 1.31).

Figure 3: Modelled development of different scenario variables throughout the 21st century in South-west Messinia.

7. VARIABLE: POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

A key external variable in the SD model for this Greek case is the implementation of European policies at the national level and whether these policies can prevent a possible collapse of the lagoon system. Another point of discussion is whether these policies will support the development of the land use spatial plan for the area. Yet, these issues mostly apply in the short run as they are based on assumptions about the effective implementation of the most recent Common Agricultural Policy or the Biodiversity Strategy. It is not possible to predict possible future changes of these policies during the coming decades. However, we did try to include some relevant storylines covering these longer-term evolutions in the scenario descriptions presented on the previous pages. We added scenario lines for the implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) as “EU policy implementation (CAP)” and for the NATURA 2000 framework as “EU policy implementation (NATURA)”. These variables are linked to several variables within the SD model (cfr. Figure 4 below).

Figure 4: Links between European policies and variables in the SD model for the Greek case.

The selected scenarios are expressed as the time needed for full adoption and implementation. They follow the same pattern. The reference value for both variables is set at 0.1 and the maximum at 1. Figure 3 (cfr. page 16) illustrates the expected implementation timeframe under each of the scenarios.

Green, integrated road

This scenario suggests that the relevant European policies will be adopted and will be fully implemented by 2030.

Unorganized, middle road

This scenario suggests that the European policies will be adopted with some delays and will be fully implemented by 2040.

Divided road

This scenario suggests that the adaptation of relevant European policies will fail and that they will not be implemented.

Rapid development

This scenario suggests that relevant European policies will be adopted with strong delays and that a full implementation status won't be reached by 2100.

COMPARISON OF THE DYNAMIC PATTERNS OF KEY MODEL VARIABLES

The integrated Greek SD model addresses the basic components of the common vision for South-west Messinia. For the selection of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) we relied on European policies - the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in particular - and broader European strategies associated with these policies, such as the Green Deal. Furthermore, the NATURA 2000 framework (NATURA) was a special point of attention, as well as the policy frameworks linked to it (e.g. the new European Biodiversity Strategy).

In this section we present the outcomes of selected KPIs in relation to:

Olive-oil production and Land Use:

- cooperative strength (Dmnl)
- GDP from olive-oil sales (Euros/Year)
- orchards under sustainable (integrated/organic) practices (ha)
- application of chemical fertilizers (%)
- Landscape Character Index (Dmnl)

Wetland restoration:

- groundwater abstractions (m^3/Year)
- groundwater availability for wetland restoration (m^3/Year)
- Mean Annual Salinity (g/Lt)
- lagoon collapse risk (Dmnl)
- biodiversity indices for vegetation, birds (Dmnl)
- potential fish catch (Kg/Year)
- expected tourists (Person/Year)

1: KPIs LINKED TO OLIVE OIL PRODUCTION AND LAND USE

The impact of the different scenarios on the variables that are used to describe olive oil production, is mainly seen via the variables “transition factors” and “changes in mentality”, which directly link to the KPIs “cooperative strength” and “orchards under sustainable practices”. This implies that they also affect the rest of the selected KPIs (cfr. Figure 5).

Having an in-depth look at the model outcomes one can observe that, when farmers join forces in co-operative schemes and adopt sustainable farming practices, the olive oil sector will benefit from improved branding and marketing, as well as from a reduction of chemical inputs and prudent water use. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we noticed the following under the different scenarios:

Green, integrated road

- The GDP from olive oil sales is expected to increase with 6% during the period 2041-2050 and with almost 22% during the period 2071-2080.
- The cultivation costs are expected to decrease with 2% during the period 2041-2050 and with almost 7% in the period 2071-2080.
- The application of chemical fertilizers is expected to increase with almost 3% during the years 2041-2050 and by almost 14% in the period 2071-2080.
- The water demand for irrigation is expected to increase with 1% during the years 2041-2050, yet to decrease with 4% during the period 2071-2080 when more farmers start to irrigate according to the trees’ needs.

Figure 5: Modelling results for the KPIs linked to olive oil production in South-west Messina.

Unorganized, middle road

- The GDP from olive oil sales is expected to increase with about 3% during the years 2041-2050 and with 0,5% during the period 2071-2080.
- The cultivation costs are expected to decrease with 2% in the period 2041-2050 and with almost 3% during the years 2071-2080.
- The application of chemical fertilizers (% of land treated with chemical fertilizers) is expected to decrease with 2% by the middle of this century (2041-2050) and with almost 6% during the years 2071-2080. This decreasing trend is mainly a result of the loss of agricultural land in favor of build-up land (cfr. Figure 6 below).
- The demand for irrigation water is expected to increase with 2% during the years 2041-2050 and to decrease with 0,4% in the second half of this century (2071-2080).

Divided road

- The GDP from olive oil sales is expected to decrease with 1% during the years 2041-2050 and with 6% during the period 2071-2080.
- The cultivation costs are expected to decrease with 0,4% in 2041-2050 and with almost 0,5% during the years 2071-2080.
- The application of chemical fertilizers is expected to increase with 1% during the period 2041-2050 and with almost 3% during the years 2071-2080. This decreasing trend is mainly a result of the loss of agricultural land in favor of build-up land (cfr. Figure 6).
- The demand for irrigation water is expected to increase with 2% during the years 2041-2050, yet to decrease with 2% during the second half of the century (2071-2080).

Rapid development

- The GDP from olive-oil sales is expected to decrease with 0,3% during the years 2041-2050 and to further decline by almost 3% in the period 2071-2080.
- The cultivation costs are expected to decrease with 2% by the middle of the century (2041-2050) and to become even lower (a decrease of almost 6%) in the years 2071-2080.
- The application of chemical fertilizers is expected to increase with 2% during the years 2041-2050 and to increase even more with 5% during the second half of the century (2071-2080). This decreasing trend is mainly affected by the loss of agricultural land in favor of build-up land (cfr. Figure 6).
- The demand for irrigation water is expected to increase by 2% in 2041-2050 and to decrease

Figure 6: Modelling results for the KPIs linked to olive oil production in South-west Messina.

by 1% later on (2071-2080) due to farmer practices aligning more and more with the irrigation needs of the trees.

2: KPIS LINKED TO WETLAND RESTORATION

The impact of the different scenarios on the variables that are used to describe wetland restoration, can mainly be noticed via the variables “restoration of natural flows” and “water availability”, which both affect the variable “Mean Annual Salinity (MAS)”. The MAS is considered as a central KPI within the model and it is connected to several other KPIS.

The compilation of graphs in Figure 7, illustrates how the delay in restoration actions could affect the wetland status (biodiversity: vegetation, birds’ index) and the associated economic activities (fishing: fish catch and tourism: collapse risk, annual tourism).

In the model we assume that restoration efforts (reconnection with fresh water inputs from the catchment) can be realized once the EU policy index reaches a value of 0.58 (establishment, operational capacity, work preparation). Thus, under the scenarios “Green, integrated road”, “Unorganized, middle road” and “Rapid development”, the Mean Annual Salinity (MAS) is expected to decrease, be it during a different period in time. On the other hand, if the EU policy implementation remains only a paper effort, the MAS is expected to continue to increase and to reach values that are toxic for aquatic life. The model outcomes suggest that, the quicker the restoration works can start, the lower the impact on the biodiversity will be. The risk of a collapse of the ecosystem is expected to have an impact not only on the tourism sector, but also on the fishing industry in the region.

Under the scenario “**Green, integrated road**”, a collapse of the system will most likely be avoided due to immediate actions to restore the wetland. This restoration effort will favor fishing and tourism. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we notice the following:

- The Mean Annual Salinity is expected to decrease by 22% in the years 2041-2050 and by almost 22% during the period 2071-2080.
- The fish catch is expected to increase with 56% during the years 2041-2050 and by almost 60% in the period 2071-2080.
- The vegetation index is expected to improve by 335% in the years 2041-2050 and by 391% in the period 2071-2080.
- The birds index is expected to improve with 39% in the period 2041-2050, but to decrease with approximately 41% during the years 2071-2080, as more farmers start to irrigate then according to the trees’ needs.
- The risk of a collapse is expected to decrease with 82% in the period 2041-2050 and with 88% during the years 2071-2080.

Under the scenario “**Unorganized, middle road**”, a collapse of the system can most probably not avoided anymore, due to delays in the implementation of wetland restoration actions. This will have serious implications on biodiversity, fishing and tourism. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value we notice the following:

- The Mean Annual Salinity is expected to decrease with 5% during the years 2041-2050 and with almost 24% during the period 2071-2080.
- The fish catch is expected to increase with 13% during the years 2041-2050 and with almost 60% in the second half of the century (2071-2080).
- The vegetation index is expected to improve with about 25% by 2041-2050 and with almost 388% by 2071-2080.
- The birds index is expected to improve with almost 7% in 2041-2050 and with 41% by 2071-2080.
- The collapse risk is expected to decrease with 17% in the period 2041-2050 and with almost

88% in the period 2071-2080. Nonetheless, a tentative collapse is expected to have a temporal effect on the number of expected tourists, which is expected to recover after the restoration work.

Under the scenario “**Divided road**” any effort to restore the ecosystem remains only on paper as a result of which the wetland collapses with permanent and serious damage for the biodiversity in the region. Automatically, this also impacts the fishing industry. The tourism sector, however, does not seem to experience much impact as it mainly relies on 3S-mass tourism. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we notice the following:

- The Mean Annual Salinity is expected to increase with 74% in the period 2041-2050 and with almost 164% during the period 2071-2080.
- The fish catch is expected to decrease with about 97% by the years 2041-2050 and with almost 100% in the period 2071-2080. A collapse of the lagoon system will therefore terminate any fishing activities in the region.
- The vegetation index is expected to decrease with 100% in 2041-2050 and remain the same during the rest of the period.
- The birds index is expected to increase with almost 40% in the years 2041-2050, and by 43,2% in 2071-2080.
- The collapse risk is expected to reach a maximum value by 2030.

Figure 7: SD model results for KPIs linked to wetland restoration in South-west Messinia.

Under the scenario “**Rapid development**” a collapse of the lagoon system cannot be avoided anymore due to prolonged delays in the implementation of actions for wetland restoration. It should be possible to overcome the implications for biodiversity, fishing and tourism. Though this will take many years. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we notice the following:

- The Mean Annual Salinity is expected to increase with 68% in the period 2041-2050 and to decrease with almost 24% in the period 2071-2080 after thorough restoration works.
- The fish catch is expected to decrease with 96% by the years 2041-2050. After the restoration works, however, this value is expected to increase again with 60% by the years 2071-2080. For a long period of time fishing won't be possible, but the activity is expected to recover in the longer term.
- The vegetation index is expected to decrease with 100% by the years 2041-2050. After the restoration works, this value is expected to increase with almost 380% in the period 2071-2080, as the availability of fresh water will again create favourable conditions for the local fauna and flora.
- The birds index is expected to increase with 39% in the period 2041-2050. After the restoration works, this value is expected to increase with 41% by the years 2071-2080.
- The collapse risk is expected to reach a maximum value already by 2030. After restoration, this value is expected to decrease with almost 88% during the years 2071-2080.

Apart from the implementation of certain policies, wetland restoration is also affected by the availability of fresh water resources. Of special focus is the groundwater aquifer of Tyflomitis, which is partly used for the water supply of the municipality (30%). Besides this, it is also used for irrigation by the local farmers (30% of catchment farmers). For as long as the abstracted volumes do not affect the stock of the aquifer (6,500,000 m³), most of the remaining water volume is discharged as surface water (springs), which where once feeding the wetland.

The compilation of graphs in Figure 8 below, illustrates how the increase in groundwater abstractions could impact the groundwater stocks and reduce the water availability for wetland restoration.

Figure 8: SD model results for KPIs linked to groundwater availability in South-west Messinia.

Due to climate change (RCP 2.6), the availability of fresh water is expected to decrease. In the context of restoration actions, however, it is important to understand how much water can be available for wetland restoration under each of the scenarios. As illustrated in Figure 8, the long-term average of water availability for wetland restoration under the scenario **"Green, integrated road"** is 817,159 m³/year, which is 18% higher than under the scenario **"Unorganized, middle road"**, 21% higher than under the scenario **"Divided road"** and 31% higher when compared to the scenario **"Rapid development"**.

Under the first scenario, namely **"Green, integrated road"**, groundwater abstractions are expected to increase with 3% by the years 2041-2050. Though they will decrease again with 2% by the years 2071-2080, as people start to use less water in their everyday life. Because of this evolution, the groundwater aquifer remains in a good state, which results in an adequate water volume for wetland restoration. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we see the following:

- The groundwater stock is expected to decrease with 5% by the years 2041-2050 and with 1% during the second half of the century (2071-2080).
- The amount of groundwater available for the wetlands is expected to decrease with 30% by 2041-2050, which if further toned down to 6% in the years 2071-2080.

Under the scenario **"Unorganized, middle road"** groundwater abstractions are expected to increase in volume with 13% by the years 2041-2050 and with 25% during the second half of the century (2071-2080), which increases the risk of affecting the permanent stock of the aquifer. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we observe the following:

- The groundwater stock is expected to decrease with 7% in the period 2041-2050 and with 5% during the period 2071-2080.
- The groundwater available for the wetland is expected to decrease with 39% by the middle of the century (2041-2050) and with almost 30% during the years 2071-2080.

Under the scenario **"Divided road"** the groundwater abstractions are expected to increase with 15% during the period 2041-2050, and to even increase with almost 29% during the second half of the century (2071-2080). This increases the risk of affecting the permanent stock of the aquifer substantially. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we observe the following:

- The groundwater stock is expected to decrease with 7% during the years 2041-2050 and with almost 6% during the following period (2071-2080).
- The groundwater available for the wetland is expected to decrease with 40% during the period 2041-2050 and with almost 33% during the years 2071-2080.

Under the scenario **"Rapid development"** groundwater abstractions are expected to increase with 18% during the years 2041-2050 and with almost 42% in the years 2071-2080 - again increasing the risk of affecting the permanent stock of the aquifer. When compared to the 2011-2020 average annual value, we observe the following:

- The groundwater stock is expected to decrease with 7% in the period 2041-2050 and with almost 8% during the period 2071-2080. The risk to permanently damage the aquifer stock is very high.
- The groundwater available for the wetland is expected to decrease with 40% in the years 2041-2050 and with almost 33% during the period 2071-2080.

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